

MANIFESTATION OF SPEECH ACTS IN RADIO ADVERTISING TEXTS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the representation of speech acts in radio advertising texts, it highlights the impact of speech acts on the addressee and the features of their motivation to action. Also, the linguistic tools that serve the expression of speech acts in radio advertising texts and the determination of the purpose of radio advertisers are analyzed on the materials of radio advertising texts.*

Keywords: *radio advertising texts, radio advertisers, pragma linguistics, speech acts, locative act, illocative act, perlocutionary act, Advertising communication, pragmatic barrier, propositional act, pragmatic presupposition.*

Speech acts are one of the central issues of pragma linguistics. Speech acts are important to understand the speech goal between the addresser and the addressee in the process of any communicative dialogue. Therefore, it is important to determine the purpose of radio advertisers on the basis of radio advertising materials. Advertising communication takes place between advertisers and consumers.

The focus of advertising communication is “the impact of the word on the recipient, the increase in the awareness of the goal, changes in the emotional state, the views and evaluations of the recipient, and the effect on the actions taken”.[1]

Advertisers make good use of speech acts. Their purpose is not simply to provide information to the addressee through advertising texts. Maybe influence consumers and encourage them to act accordingly. That is, persuasion to buy the product.

The speech act theory was introduced by Austin in 1962. He pointed out that we do three things when pronouncing a sentence. The first is locative (the act of saying something), the second is descriptive (the purpose of saying something) and the third is elocutionary (the effect produced by saying).[2]

Advertisers use language as a tool to attract customers and compel them to buy a product. Kotler (1996) states that the main purpose of advertising is to convey the important message that needs to be conveyed. this is usually conveyed through images and written forms. It is important that the message in the advertisement is conveyed effectively, otherwise the purpose of the communication will be lost and the process will be disrupted. Suyanto (2007) states that advertisements use elegant language to encourage positive responses from readers. If the intention of the advertiser is not fully understood by the buyers, the essence of the advertisement will fail.

Searle 1994 further expanded the study of speech acts and defined them as basic and minimal units of linguistic communication. He classifies the speech act as indicative, strict, declarative, task. Van Dijk (1992) distinguishes speech act as micro speech act and macro speech act. Micro speech acts are individual speech acts and macro speech acts or global speech acts are the whole speech. According to Dake, advertising and narrative discourse are generally associated with global speech acts. (Van Dake, 1992). Brinker divides speech acts into five textual categories,

taking into account the pragmatic function of speech and interpersonal relations. i.e. divided into information, obligation, appeal, declaration and communication functions.[3]

Speech act theory was first introduced by Austin who divided it into three acts; locative, perlocative and illocutive. Searle (1979) worked to categorize these acts. According to Searle, speech acts are "words that have a functional function in language and communication. Searle classified illocutionary acts as affirmative, directive, commissive, expressive, declarative. Affirmatives are speech acts that the speaker seeks to be true. Validators can be true or false. These include suggestions, statements, answers, inferences, predictions, disagreements, etc. Directives are speech acts in which the speaker urges the listener to do something. Instructions can be obeyed or disobeyed. These include commands, requests, requests, etc. Commissions speak of the speaker's future voluntary action. These include promises, guarantees, etc. Expressive actions are actions that show the speaker's feelings and emotions about something. These include thanking, apologizing, welcoming, congratulating, etc. Declaratives are speech acts that change the state of an external situation, thing, or event. These are declarations that change external states. For example, dismissal, censure, announcement and appointment.[4]

The emergence and study of the speech act problem in linguistics is connected with the philosophical views of the Australian philosopher L.Wittgenstein on the issue of linguistic activity. The theory of the speech act was first put forward by the English philosopher J.Austin. He focused on the development of the theory of the speech act, in particular, on the analysis of performative verbs that form the speech act, and on the issue of classifying the types of speech act. In the book "How to do things with words" published after J. Austin's death, the views of the scientist on this issue were summarized.[5]

J.Austin's concept of the speech act was first analyzed by Z.Wendler, J.Searle, its achievements and shortcomings were shown and developed with new views.[6] Later, this problem was expressed in the linguistic views of V.Humboldt, S.Balli, S.Karsevsky, L.P.Yakubinsky, K.L.Buhler, E.Benveniste, M.M.Bakhtin and others.

The issues of speech activity and speech act in Russian linguistics were studied by V.N.Zabavnikov, A.A.Leontev, A.N.Baranov, G.Y.Kreidlin, I.N.Gorelov, S.A.Sukhikh and others, the existing views on this issue were summarized and supplemented.[7]

The problem of speech act in Uzbek linguistics was specially studied by M.Hakimov [8]. In the second chapter of his doctoral dissertation, entitled "Pragmatic interpretation of the text in Uzbek", the issue of the formation, types, and study of the speech act was analyzed. In the study, according to the general semiological sign of the speech act, the speech act (locative), communicative (illocutive), propositional, speech effect (perlocution) acts recognized by many linguists were treated. In this research, the scientist classified the manifestations of the speech act based on J.R.Searle's concept and revealed the essence of each type based on Uzbek language texts. M.Hakimov classified speech acts as follows:

1. Representative or message speech act. 2. Acts of obligation. 3. Expressive acts. 4. Declarative act. [9]

The problem of the speech act was covered in separate chapters in Sh.Safarov's book "Pragmalinguistics". The scientist evaluated the place of speech act theory in pragmalinguistic theory, analyzed the views of linguists about the speech act one by one and expressed a critical reaction to them; gave detailed information about the locative, illocutionary and perlocutionary

types of the speech act and indirectly enriched the theoretical views about the speech act with new knowledge. [10]

Although there are many research works devoted to the analysis of the problem of speech act in world linguistics, the concept of speech act is interpreted differently in them, its manifestations are classified differently. According to J.Austin and J.Searle, the founders of the theory of speech act, speech act means an elementary speech act that expresses a certain content and is described based on the rules of language.

J.Austin stated that the following is performed in the speech act: pronunciation of specific sounds belonging to the universally recognized language code; form a sentence based on grammatical rules from words belonging to this language; providing the sentence with content, reference, etc.; creating speech usages and coordinating with reality; orienting speech usages to a specific purpose, turning them into an illocutionary act; achieving the desired result, influencing the mind or behavior of the addressee, creating a new speech situation. [11]

According to T.V.Jerebilo, the speech act is a psychophysical process that reflects the speech communication between the speaker (addressee) and the listener (addressee) and consists of the following components:

1) speaking (writing); 2) perception; 3) understanding speech (text). [12]

According to Sh.Safarov, "speech act is a linguistic address of the speaker to the listener in a specific environment, with a specific purpose", "speech act is the pronunciation of a certain sentence in a specific communication environment", "speech act is a "building material" for communication, it does not reflect the logical continuity of the communicative process. [13]

M.Hakimov defined the speech act as follows: "The concept of a speech act is a description of the relationship of acts of mutual meaning that occur in the process of communication and interaction between people". [14]

M.Hakimov notes that the following components are generally involved in a speech act: speaker, listener, object of speech - factual material and speech situation. [15] According to M.Kurbanova, the general language knowledge and language skills of the speech participants should be included among the components necessary for the effectiveness of the speech act. If the participants of the speech do not have knowledge of a common language (even sign language), the speech act is not only incomprehensible to the parties, but also its realization is unlikely.

Since the speech act is subordinated to a specific communicative goal of the speaker, its various forms are different. In particular, a speech form expressing a command forms a command speech act, a speech fragment expressing a question forms an interrogative speech act, and a speech form expressing a desire forms a desire speech act. In the sources, types of speech acts are noted, such as reporting, speech acts aimed at expressing a desire, acts of obligation, forms of social etiquette, acts expressing emotionality, approving, prohibiting, speech-stopping acts. [16]

In the classification of J.Austin, types of speech acts are distinguished, such as locution, illocution, perlocution. [17] J.Searle distinguished the following types of speech act: pronunciation act, propositional act creating reference and predication, illocutionary act showing the speaker's purpose. J.Searle focused on studying the illocutionary act. [18]

In the theory of the speech act, the power of the illocutionary act introduced by J.Austin and the question of the classification of illocutionary act types based on it occupy a central place. Based on performative verbs, J.Austin distinguished types of illocutionary acts such as verdictive, exercitive, commissive, passive, expository. J. Searle, unlike J. Austin, distinguished the following

types of illocutionary act based on 12 criteria based on the act itself and not on verbs: representatives, directives, commissives, expressives, declaratives. [19]

Each of the types of speech acts distinguished by J.Austin and J.Searle is sufficiently interpreted and reacted to in the sources. [20]

It is known that the concept of locative act introduced by J.Austin in the theory of speech act is used in pragmalinguistics in relation to the act of speaking. According to M.Hakimov, “the speaker's perception of the reality in the objective world and the level of its verbal and non-verbal expression reflect the concept of locution in a certain sense”. [21] If you pay attention, in the interpretation of M.Hakimov, locution also covers the non-verbal expression of reality. However, the scientist notes in another place that “the normative pronunciation process of phonetic, lexical and syntactic units is considered by the speaker as a locutionary act”. [22] According to M.Kurbanova, although the non-verbal expression of communication is a component of the speech act, it does not intersect at the same point with the locative act (speaking). [23]

Sh.Safarov, while noting this aspect specific to the locutionary act, states the following: “In the process of communication, we create a meaningful linguistic word and perform a speech activity by pronouncing it, the performance of the same activity is a locutionary act (locutionary act). If for some reason (not knowing the language, being dumb) a meaningful sentence is not formed and it is not pronounced, the locative action does not occur”. [24]

I.P.Susov notes that the locative act is an aspect of the pronunciation of a sentence with a phonetic, lexical-grammatical and semantic structure, the realization of the sound side of the sentence is related to the phonetic act, the realization of the lexical-grammatical structure is related to the phatic act, and the realization of the semantic structure is related to the rhetorical act. [25]

M.Hakimov “the normative pronunciation process of phonetic, lexical, syntactic units is considered by the speaker as a locative act”, “the essence of the locative act is clarified by the pronunciation of the sentence using certain grammatical rules”, “the locative aspect of the speech act is only sound, is limited to the correct pronunciation of words and devices based on certain lexical and grammatical rules”. [26]

In radio advertising texts, it is assumed that information will be delivered to the consumer in a clear and understandable manner. Therefore, the locative act is expressed in advertising texts without departing from the norms of speech. Let's see in the following advertisement example:

"Taronas media" presents in cooperation with "Navo" TV channel!

On December 23-24, at 19:00, the New Year's gala concert "Taronas show" will be held in the "Friendship of Peoples" concert hall.

Munisa Rizaeva, Nilufar Usmanova, Ulugbek Rahmatullaev, Rayhon, Shahrukhkhan, Bojalar, VIA Marokanda, Sahar, Umidakhon, Mushtari-Zafar, Ozoda, Sarvar and Kamil, Afruz group and others will take part in the program.

Information support is the "Uzbegin taronasi" radio station.

Played by phonogram. (r. "Uzbegin Taronasi")

It seems that this advertising text was prepared on the basis of phonetic, lexical, grammatical and semantic standards of speech. Advertisers ensure that advertising information reaches the addressee correctly and clearly. After all, the emergence of a communicative pragmatic barrier between the addresser and the addressee does not give the desired result in the field of advertising. It is important to fully understand and understand the proposition reflected in the speech act in advertising texts.

Goods and services are presented to the general public through advertising texts. Information about the subject of speech expressed in a speech act is a propositional act. The propositional act was introduced by J.Searle as a separate type of act.

Propositional act is the expression of a message about a reality by way of confirmation or denial.

Get a loan at home and get money within 5 minutes through the TBC application. Buy equipment for your home, travel abroad or start your own business with a loan without a guarantor, collateral or documents. TBC bank - we make people's lives easier. (r. "Uzbeginim Taronasi")

In this advertising text, it is emphasized that advertising information is delivered to the addressee through confirmation, that is, by installing the TBC application on a smartphone, it is possible to get money and use it for various purposes.

Even in the chill, high-quality rums do not deform or turn yellow. "Akva" efficiency is with us. (r. "Oriat Dono")

In this advertising text, the information is expressed by way of denial that aqua frames do not deform and do not turn yellow under any conditions.

These forms of speech are considered a propositional act as they express information about the object of speech through a message. However, the act of pronouncing in the expression of the propositional act indicates that it intersects with the locative act at one point. Similarly, the fact that the speaker's communicative intention - the intention to inform about the event - is fulfilled through a propositional act means that this act is also considered an illocutionary act. In other words, a propositional act has a complex structure, in which it is possible to observe a combination of several types of acts.

An illocutionary act is a type of communication related to the act of speaking that reflects a specific purpose of the speaker. In the illocutionary act, the purpose of the speaker has an overt or hidden expression. How to express the communicative purpose depends on the subject of the speech. Sometimes the speaker directly expresses his purpose of creating a speech act, sometimes his purpose is hidden in the speech act. [29]

In advertising texts, the purpose of advertisers is sometimes expressed openly, sometimes secretly.

Is it inconvenient to ask for a loan from relatives or acquaintances?

In that case, get a micro-loan of up to 50 million soums in the application "on the spot" of the industrial construction bank, without queues, guarantors, collateral and documents. Try it. Download the "in-place" app from playmarket or appstore. (r. "Oriat Dono")

In this ad text, the hidden goal of the advertiser was revealed by asking a question. That is, is it inconvenient to ask for a loan from relatives or acquaintances? It is inconvenient to ask for a loan from your relatives or acquaintances through the question, we will help you in this matter without any problems, the confirmation is emphasized. From the point of view of the activity of commercial banks at the expense of loan interest, attracting customers is applied in order to increase their number.

The illocutionary acts of confirmation, questioning, command, desire, advice, promise, and warning are found in radio advertising texts. Such meaningful types of the speech act are sometimes formed in accordance with the syntactic structure, and sometimes have a hidden expression through presupposition. The types of speech acts often found in radio advertising texts can be semantically classified as follows:

Message act:

From the twenty-eighth to the thirtieth of December and from the second to the ninth of January at the Palace of "Friendship of Peoples" there is a show called "New Year's Pirates" for children! (r. "Oriat Dono")

2) Questioning act:

- yes, Muzaffar, peace? I don't like the way you look. Mabodo, isn't your blood pressure rising?

- What does blood pressure do at my age?

- My child, you should always measure yourself after you are over forty! Do you have a blood pressure gauge?

- no, where can I get it?

- Ah, you are advertising yourself! We have been using "little doctor" tonometers at home for 10 years.

- really?

- Yes!

"Little Doctor" tonometers - convenient, easy and high-quality. (r. "Navruz")

3) Request act:

Hello, Santa Claus! Please don't give anything this year! Because we bought everything from Technomark.

Guaranteed gift to every buyer for purchases over 1 million soums. (r. "Uzbegin Taronasi")

4) Command act:

Get comfortable, cheer up, choose your direction, enjoy every distance traveled as a Chevrolet tracker. After all, it is designed according to your requirements. Always be in the spotlight or on your way to the news with it. Chevrolet tracker is everything you want!

(r. "Uzbegin Taronasi")

5) act of encouragement:

Are you ready for Umrah?

"Alfa tour" offers you: 4-5 star hotels, 24/7 medical assistance, quick response team in Makkah and Madinah. Call now and fulfill one of the pillars of Islam today: (r. "Oriat Dono")

6) Promise act:

Shopping cart is waiting for you. We have prepared hundreds of discounts and nice bonuses for you. We are waiting for you at the address 4/3 of Ahmad Yugnaki district. The basket is closer than usual! (r. "Oriat Dono")

7) offer act:

- Do you like to eat soup?

- Yes!

- at night? or in the morning? Or at any time?

- yes, pilaf!

- then please visit the "The Plow" cooking center. You can eat delicious pilaf for 24 hours or we will deliver it to you. "The plow" is pilaf. (r. "Navruz")

8) Desire act:

Do you want to own the car of your dreams? But you can't save enough money?

Dreams come true with the car loan offered by the mortgage bank.

Full or 50 percent financing, no down payment required for payroll projects, and the bank also offers auto loans to the secondary market.

Mortgage bank - we create an opportunity! (r. "Vodiy sadosi")

9) Warning act:

Tashkent region emergency department warns!

Dear citizens, fire safety month is being held in our country. We ask you to strictly observe the fire safety rules in order to prevent fires and their consequences, poisoning of citizens and accidents related to the flash of gas-air mixture that may occur during the month.

Dear compatriots and guests of our country, let's protect our property from fires by strictly following the rules of fire safety!

(r. "Oriat Dono")

10) Savings act:

News from Zilyonny chai!

It saves you both time and money. (r. "Navruz")

11) act of surprise:

- this has never happened before!

- what?

- it didn't happen!

- what didn't happen?

- I'm telling you, it didn't happen!

- tell me, what happened?

- Tenge Bank's "Navroz Kelibon" campaign! Apply for a new car at any of the bank's offices and win a master card as a gift with a deposit of three hundred thousand soums. (r. "Oriat Dono")

12) Guarantee act:

With a mortgage bank, your money is not only protected, but also guaranteed. To do this, download the ipotalitel mobile application and place your funds in a convenient online deposit. The deposit is accepted for a period of 24 months in the amount of 22 percent per annum. Deposits are guaranteed by the Fund for Guaranteeing Citizens' Deposits in Banks. (r. "Uzbegim taronasi")

13) act of promptness:

You can top up Capital Bank cards from any Russian card.

Rubles in Russia, soums or dollars at the capital bank immediately! Instant with only 1 percent commission. Everything is in the capital bank mobile application. Fast, useful and convenient! (r. "Vodiy sadosi")

From the examples given by these advertising texts, it is clear that the main goal is to sell the product. However, advertisers define the communicative goal with customers differently. For this purpose, they make effective use of the above-mentioned types of illacitive act. In particular, in advertising texts, affirmative, interrogative, and command acts of the inductive act are widely used. In the process of analyzing radio advertisements, we were convinced that the act of denial is very rare.

A perlocutionary act influences the feelings of the addressee and prompts them to perform certain actions.

In advertisements, information is encoded using language features and updated more implicitly. Hidden information gives a high value to the object and is accepted without question.

It is slightly controlled by the mind and used for manipulation. The effectiveness of hidden information is based on the difficult mechanism of its reception and interpretation by the recipient.

The pragmatic function of hidden advertising information is its action towards the addressee. Presupposition is the most important expression of hidden information in advertising strategy.

Pragmatic presupposition is a central element describing the advertising context. because it creates the conditions for understanding the statement, recalling the knowledge and beliefs of the speaker and receiver.

Do you believe it is safe to keep your earnings at home? Don't risk it! It is better to entrust your money to Turon Bank's high-interest national and foreign currency deposits. Turon bank is a symbol of stability. (r. "Oriat Dono")

Do you believe that Turon Bank is safe to keep your money earned through this advertisement at home? He affects people's feelings through his question. In other words, this rhetorical question means that it is dangerous to keep the funds earned at home. Their purpose is understood through the next sentence of the ad. That is, do not risk! It is better to entrust your money to Turon Bank's high-interest national and foreign currency deposits.

Advertisers emphasize that the product is useful and necessary in their advertising texts. For this, they take into account the psychological conditions of people. That is, a certain time limit is given to sell the product. As a result, buyers will not have the opportunity to think about it. It will be necessary to make an urgent and quick decision.

Become the owner of a modern Chery crossover. It is possible to pay in 12-month installments for Chery cars only in July. (r. "Uzbegin Taronasi")

The use of softer lines constructed in the form of dialogue is also common. As a rule, this method is used in indirect speech acts:

- It's been winter this year, dad! It was especially cold, up to minus twenty-twenty three degrees!

- We are preparing to change the windows...

- Alutex!

- Alutex?

- Yes, alutex!

- Modern thermal profiles from Alutex! (r. "Vodiy sadosi")

The text of this advertisement is given in the voice of a family woman and a man. It may seem like a normal family conversation, but it's not. This situation will be repeated by reminding that this year the winter was severe and people suffered from it is indicated that it is possible. For this, Alutex windows are offered as the most suitable solution for heat preservation.

The purpose of the advertising message is to encourage the addressee to buy goods, and the effect on the emotional level of the recipient significantly increases the attractiveness of the advertised object. It also explains that all advertising messages are permeated with an emotional-evaluative lexicon that creates positive lasting associations with the product being offered.

The tradition of cooking soup in our country has been going on for a thousand years. Today, our festive tables are filled with pilaf. The aromas of roasted rice and delicious spices whet your appetite. Delicious soups are brewed day and night in large pots of "The plow" near station d/2 of Yunusabad district. "The plow"! Order delicious Uzbek food for 24 hours. We will deliver to your address "The plow". "the plow" is a place for real lovers of pilaf. (r. "Navruz")

The advertisement begins with the music of Farrukh Zakirov's song "Tea House". "The Plow" cooking center reminds of national values through this advertising text and emphasizes that the table is filled with pilaf. He recognizes the superiority of soup over other dishes. The aromas of cooked rice and delicious spices whet the appetite, he tries to influence people through his words, and the sound of the soup boiling in the pot is heard. The cooking center promises to deliver food to order 24/7, and the doorbell will ring on the spot.

Advertisers use celebrities, such as singers, actors, etc., to create a positive impression on the mind of the addressee. This is positively received by the population.

Install Imzo frame,
Forget your problems.
In the factory for you
Exactly produced.
It's cold or hot outside,
"Imzo" is not interesting to them.
Any time you want
We will install it for you. (r. "Vodiy sadosi")

The text of this advertisement is performed by the famous singer T.Sodikov instead of the words of his most popular song.

Acknowledging the reliability of the product in advertising texts has a positive effect on the buyer.

Reliable Russian steel that has passed the test of time!

Ideal geometric dimensions for fast drilling, multi-stage quality control on Japanese equipment. All this is for the creation of "Mekhmash" universal products.

Mekhmash is a masterful example of quality. (r. "Oriat Dono")

Offering gifts for purchases is one of the most popular forms of influencing.

We are waiting for you in the shopping cart every day from 8:00 am to 12:00 pm with many promotions, discounts and pleasant gifts. Basket - closer than usual. (r. "Vodiy sadosi")

In conclusion, the expression of speech acts in radio advertising texts affects the addressee and motivates customers to buy products and use services. For this, Uzbek radio advertising texts were analyzed according to speech acts. This shows that the representation of illocutive and perlocutive acts in Advertising texts gives effective results for Advertisers. Influence by persuasion motivates them to act. Therefore, advertising information should be strong.

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